

1 **Activation of RBM5 by HPV16 E7.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Rbm5* by HPV16
9 HPV E7.

10 Citations

11 1. McLaughlin-Drubin, M.E. and Münger, K., 2009. The human papillomavirus E7 oncoprotein.
12 *Virology*, 384(2), pp.335-344.

13 2. Bonnal, S., Martínez, C., Förch, P., Bachi, A., Wilm, M. and Valcárcel, J., 2008.
14 RBM5/Luca-15/H37 regulates Fas alternative splice site pairing after exon definition. *Molecular cell*, 32(1),
15 pp.81-95.

16 GSE240750
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28